

Classroom observation

Why is peer observation better in teaching process?

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Annotation

The article is primarily concerned with classroom observation, above all *peer observation*, and its importance in teaching. Moreover, it points out that peer observation itself helps teachers to *understand* what they need to see while doing it and to first of all *develop* and then *improve* their understanding of pedagogical skills.

Key words: summative observation, formative observation, pre-observation, while-observation, post-observation (debriefing).

Аннотация

Статья в первую очередь посвящена наблюдению в классе, прежде всего наблюдению со стороны сверстников, и его важности в обучении. Более того, указывается, что само по себе коллегиальное наблюдение помогает учителям понять, что им нужно увидеть при этом, и в первую очередь развить, а затем улучшить свои понимания о педагогических навыках.

Ключевые слова: итоговое наблюдение, формирующее наблюдение, предварительное наблюдение, во время наблюдения, пост-наблюдение (подведение итогов).

Everyone is aware of what exactly 'classroom observation' means, but can we safely say that they are aware of its great importance to the teaching process and teacher himself? A classroom observation is an excellent way to have an ideal opportunity for

getting different viewpoints on teaching. Moreover, with the help of it, we are capable of gaining some new insights into the teaching procedure.

So, there are distinctively different forms of classroom observation. For example, it can be a summative observation and formative observation. A summative observation is an evaluative observation in which an administrator or the head of department observes the class. The main purpose of this procedure is to rate first of all the teacher and then students. As for the other form, it is a friendly observation in which two colleagues or peers observe one another's classes. Improving teaching skills and professional development is the purpose of formative observation. A formative observation is known as a peer observation as well.

A formative peer observation is beneficial to both the observed teacher and the teacher doing the observation. For example, it can help the observed teacher to fill gaps in information that he may not have recognized their importance in teaching. And the observer can find out his unrecognised strengths that he might have not paid much attention or else valued in his teaching.

A peer observation is a simple way of gaining new insights into the teaching procedure. It makes an observer think and look for the ideas or changes which can be implemented in a classroom. Furthermore, they can develop a new method or approach for their own subject and course. From a social point of view, a peer observation is a kind of facilitated conversation which can lead to more friendly and broader conversations. That's to say it is an easy way of making friends with your colleagues.

However, it is impossible to learn and observe everything about someone's teaching way from this one observation or let's say *encounter*. Because when you observe a class, you are seeing only a part of the experience. If an observation is carefully organised, there is a higher possibility to benefit more though. So, there are three steps of a successful observation.

1. Preparing for the observation.
2. Observing in the class.
3. The post observation – debriefing.

There are some essentially important questions that require answers during each step so as to successfully observe a class. Both the observer and the observed teacher needs to pay attention and cover every single one of them. They need to look for the answers of these questions...

	Pre-observation	While-observation	Post-observation
1.	What kind of information should they gather from each other?	Where should the observer sit?	What kind of information should they exchange?
2.	To what should the observer pay attention during the observation?	How should the observed teacher behave during having a lesson?	What does the observer like about the performance of the observed teacher?
3.	How should they interact with one another during this stage?	How should the observer behave during the observation?	What kind of suggestions does the observer give?
4.			How should the debriefing end?

In the first stage, as a peer observation is collaborative and mutual, two teachers should choose a free time so as to speak with one another about the preparation process. They need to have a conversation about what to do or observe in the class well ahead of the time of planned peer observation. Even there is a special pre-observation guidebook where you can find steps to follow.

Mostly peer observations are effective and successful when they ask questions from the teacher being observed like what information the observer needs to know about the class and to what they need to pay attention during the lesson. For instance, they must know what aspects of the course, teaching strategies or learning goals they are observing.

Another example related to this stage is that while I was doing a peer observation, I was required to pay heed to the relationship and interaction between the teacher and students, the information given to the students (whether it is appropriate or not) and the speed of the teacher (whether it is slow or fast).

In the second stage, the observer should silently enter the classroom and sit at the back of the class. He needs to bring some sheet of paper to jot down important parts of the lesson or the parts where he misunderstood so that it will be easier to give feedback on the performance and ask questions later. Moreover, he needs to analyse the behaviours of the observed teacher and students.

In the debriefing session, both of the teachers interact with each other thoroughly. The observer talks about what he liked during the observation process by praising some of the observed teacher's qualities. He mentions her performance and gives suggestions for improvements for the class. For example, by using the notes the observer used in the class, he can ask questions about the points he didn't understand during the observation and highlights the pedagogical moments so as to make some compliments on the observed teacher. Or he can give feedback on his colleague where she did well, and he is going to implement that approach in his own class. Or else he can emphasise the speed of her speech where she appropriately slowed down and where she went through faster and vice versa...

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